

FAMILY AND SCHOOL PROBLEMS FACED BY SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: A SURVEY

Gagandeep Kaur¹, Ph.D. & Miss Manpreet Kaur²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Guru Nanak Dev, University, Amritsar

Email: dhillongagan449@gmail.com

²M.Ed. student, Department of Education, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar

Email: manubhagat29553@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

The present study aims to find out the different problems (family and school) faced by secondary school students. This study also focused on the family and school problems in relation to gender, locale, and working and non-working status of mothers among government senior secondary school students. A total of 200 senior secondary school students were selected from three different schools in Amritsar district. Random sampling techniques were used for data collection. The data was collected using the questionnaire: Youth Problem Inventory (Verma, 2012). The results were analysed through percentages. Students need high counselling for family problems and school problems. All students require counselling respective of their gender, locale, and working and non-working mothers status.

KEYWORDS:- Students' family problems, school problems, senior secondary school students.

[Scholarly Research Journal's](http://www.srjis.com) is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com

INTRODUCTION

A major problem in a learner's life is stress related to education. The present educational system has become overloaded by several pressures, including the large curriculum, exam anxiety, competitiveness, etc. Research on the physical, social, and economic problems facing adolescent girls in secondary schools in the Now Gong district was undertaken by Sultana and Rasul in 1978. Her studies showed that teenage girls are more motivated to improve their social abilities. Unlike boys, girls are much more driven to participate in social activities, and boys feel far more motivated to join in social activities and feel much more encouraged to get involved in community events and integrate. Problems with students are becoming more severe

each day. The stress of school reduces happiness among learners as a result. Academic stress has at times been established as having a role. (Gogoi & Sahoo, 2019). Verma and Ojha (2005) studied the behavioural issues that teenagers face. The study's goal was to highlight the rising number of behavioural issues that teenagers are experiencing for a variety of reasons. The study placed a strong emphasis on leading a healthy lifestyle, adopting our Indian philosophy of life, creating a home that is full of love and discipline, etc. Lata (2015) study revealed that the conclusions of the study were that students of rural background studying in the school of urban areas were not well adjusted and had to face many related problems in the areas viz. social, emotional, and academic.

PROBLEMS FACED BY SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS Everywhere students are, there are numerous problems. This is also quite true in the case of India. Numerous issues have an impact on the student population. Numerous factors, including inadequate educational possibilities, the risk of unemployment, a lack of opportunities, the politicisation and criminalization of academic life, pervasive corruption and nepotism, and a host of others, demoralise students and occasionally result in law-and-order problems. Khan and Mani (2014).

EDUCATION ISSUES Children in India are suffering as a result of the strain placed on them by the school system. India's educational system evaluates students based on their achievement in the annual exam that is given at the conclusion of each semester. Pressure from parents and peers to perform well in school impedes a child's healthy growth (Khan & Mani, 2014).

SOCIAL ISSUES The way in which students approach learning, their intelligence, their attitude towards school, their socioeconomic status, and various facets of their personalities, among other things, can all have an impact on their academic success. The social issues that affect students at this stage include anger, tension, a lack of social engagement, interactions with others, and rebellion against authority figures, traditions, and practises (Bhat, 2013).

POLITICAL ISSUES The politicisation of education, government policies on education, and political meddling in educational administration all degrade educational quality. The young people of today would find it challenging to get employment due to the expanding population and reservations (Khan & Mani, 2014).

ECONOMIC ISSUES Basic and social-emotional needs of children, such as clothing, emotional support, and good social skills. Therefore, these parents' lack of foresight regarding their obligations in their children's educational processes and the lack of resources to enhance such processes could present a barrier to their achievement (Ahmar & Anwar, 2013).

CULTURAL ISSUES At educational institutions, minorities, immigrants, and foreigners face particularly difficult problems. They constantly deal with racial and cultural disparities that can obstruct their academic, social, and personal development. 2014 (Khan & Mani).

PERSONAL ISSUES Adolescents' personalities include a significant portion of their physical appearance. Concerns regarding their appearance are present. It affects how they develop personally and socially. 2017 (Parkash).

EMOTIONAL ISSUES Relationships between teachers and students are also seen as crucial for students' adjustment in the classroom (Pianta, 2001). The purpose of the current study is to analyse the perspectives on these concerns held by teachers and students alike, as well as any consequences for teacher preparation and practise (Poulou, 2017).

PHYSICAL ISSUES bodily manifestations of anxiety head heaviness and eye strain from studying, Physical issues that students experience include insomnia or excessive sleeping, exhaustion, headaches, nausea, giddiness, spells of unconsciousness, etc. 2007 (Srividhya).

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY Academic performance may be affected by a variety of psychological issues, including subclinical anxiety or depressive moods, and family stressors, including divorce, marital strife, abuse, or a family member's mental illness. In many developmental tasks, adolescents' general coping techniques are typically mirrored in their academic and social achievement in school. Teenagers who struggle with social isolation, identity problems, obsessions with their sexuality, or excessive shyness may stop participating fully in academic activities. Fear of failure, which is frequently reinforced by parents and professors, causes students to lose interest in their studies (Pianta, 2005).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study problems (family, school) among secondary school students with respect to gender.
2. To study problems (family, school) among secondary school students with respect to locale.
3. To study problems (family, school) among secondary school students with respect to the working and non-working status of mothers.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey method was used in the study. Data collection was done from secondary school students of district Amritsar. The sample of schools has been selected

randomly. The sample consists of 200 students from government senior secondary schools of Amritsar (both male and female).

INSTRUMENTS

Problems faced by secondary school students in the present study were measured using the standardized tests **YOUTH PROBLEMS INVENTORY** by Verma (2012).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT AREAS OF PROBLEMS

The problems were measured by the tool in two areas namely 1) family problems and 2) school problems.

1. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF (FAMILY PROBLEMS, SCHOOL PROBLEMS,) SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Fig 1.1 (A) Pie chart showing the percentage of family problems area wise of gender problems faced by secondary school students

According to the study's outcomes, male students encounter familial issues more frequently than female students. As a result, male students would benefit more than female students from obtaining more counselling in relation to family issues.

Fig 1.2 (B) Pie chart showing the percentage of school problems area wise of gender problems faced by secondary school students

According to the results, male students have more issues at school than their female counterparts. In order to address challenges relating to school, male students would benefit more from having more counselling support than female students.

2. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF (FAMILY PROBLEMS, SCHOOL PROBLEMS) SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO LOCALE

Fig 2.1 (A) Pie chart showing the percentage of family problems area-wise of urban & rural students to problems faced by secondary school students

Based on the study's results, kids who live in metropolitan areas encounter more family issues. In the areas of family concerns relating to urban and rural locations, they need additional counselling to address these challenges.

Fig 2.2 (B) Pie chart showing the percentage of school problems area wise of urban & rural students to problems faced by secondary school students

According to the studies, students who live in rural areas face more challenges or issues at school than students who live in urban centres. As a result, they need more counselling in regard to issues at school.

3. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF (FAMILY PROBLEMS, SCHOOL PROBLEMS) OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO WORKING AND NON-WORKING STATUS OF MOTHERS

Fig 3.1(A) Pie chart showing the percentage of family problems of non-working & working status of mothers faced by secondary school students

The result shows that students with working mothers faced more problems than those students with non-working mothers particularly in the areas of family problems. Therefore, they require more counselling in this regard.

Fig 3.2 (B) Pie chart showing the percentage of school problems of non-working & working status of mothers faced by secondary school students

The outcome shows that students with working mothers experienced significantly more issues at school than students with non-working mothers. They consequently need additional counselling in these areas.

FINDINGS

1. The study results suggest that male students experience a higher frequency of family problems than female students. Consequently, male students would benefit from receiving more counselling in the areas related to family problems than their female counterparts.
2. The results indicate that male students face a greater number of school-related problems compared to their female counterparts. As a result, male students would benefit from receiving more counselling support in addressing school-related issues than female students.
3. In the results observe that students in urban areas experience more family problems compared to those living in rural areas. They require more counselling to address these issues, in the areas of family problems w.r.t. urban areas and rural areas.
4. The results indicate that the students living in rural areas encounter more difficulties or problems in the areas of school problems compared to those in urban areas. Therefore, they require more counselling in areas of school problems.
5. The result shows that students with working mothers faced more problems than those students with non-working mothers particularly in the areas of family problems. Therefore, they require more counselling in this regard.
6. The result indicates that, In the areas of school problems, the students of working mothers faced so many more problems than those students of non-working mothers. Hence, they require more counselling in these areas.

DISCUSSION

The main objectives of the study was to understand the study problems (family and school) among secondary school students with respect to gender, the study problems (family and school) among secondary school students with respect to locale, and the study problems (family and school) among secondary school students with respect to the working and non-working status of mothers. In this study random sampling techniques. The results were analysed through

percentage analysis with respect to different areas of problems. The findings of the study all students require counselling respective of their gender, locale, and working and non-working status of mothers. For further study the perception of problems faced by secondary school students. Can be conducted in all types of area problems. These results were consistent with previous studies by Azeem (2012) Conducted a study to revealed that there was educational level of parents was very low which reduced the chance of receiving educational guidance from their parents. The results showed a crucial need for guidance for adolescents. Lata (2015) study revealed that the conclusions of the study were that students of rural background studying in the school of urban areas were not well adjusted and had to face many related problems in the areas viz. social, emotional, and academic. Boro (2017) revealed results indicated that the boys had more problems with social, emotional and educational problems when compared to the girls. So, it can be seen that many problems are faced by secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this investigation was to study family problems and school problems. This study was conducted on secondary school students. Schools are chosen from the Amritsar district of Punjab state. The present study reveals that students faced difficulties from family problems and school problems. Therefore, in every field: gender, locale, and working and non-working status of mothers students need counselling. Secondary school students who are also the basic pillars of the educational system of India need to provide all kinds of support from the family, school, society and the nation, to establish a strong community bond desirable for the progress of humankind.

REFERENCES

- Ahmar, F. & Anwar, E. (2013) Socioeconomic status and its relation to academic achievement of higher secondary school students. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 13(6), 2279-0845.
- Azeem, C.M. (2012). Educational problems of Muslim adolescents: A study with special reference to Malabar region. *Academic Research International*, 2(1), 545-556.
- Bhat, M.A. (2013) Academic achievement of secondary school students in relation to self concept and parental encouragement. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 4(6), 738-741.

- Boro, B. (2017). Adjustment problems of secondary school students of Gorkha community with respect to gender-A study. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 3(8), 341-344.
- Gogoi, M. & Sahoo, J. (2019) A study of academic stress in relation to academic achievement motivation of secondary school students. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovation Research*, 6(6), 2349-5162.
- Khan, M. & Mani, S. (2014). A study on higher secondary student's personal problems, study involvement and academic achievement. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 3 (5), 2319-7064.
- Lata, S. (2015). A study of adjustment and its related problems faced by students of rural background studying in the schools of urban areas of Delhi. *Amity International Journal of Teacher Education*, 1(1).
- Parkash, O (2017). Current status and problems of adolescents. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 3(3), 2455 – 0620.
- Pianta, R. C. (2001) The Student-Teacher Relationship Scale (STRS). Lutz, F.L: *Psychological Assessment Resources*.
- Pianta, R. C. (2005). Prevention. In H. W. Lee (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of School Psychology*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Poulou, M.S. (2017) Students emotional and behavioural difficulties: the role of teachers social and emotional learning and teacher student relationships. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 9(2), 72-89.
- Srividhya, V. (2007). Mental Health and Adjustment Problems fo Navodhaya, Central and State Schools. *Ph.D Thesis, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwar. Retrieved from google search*.
- Sultana, B. Rasul , B.(1978): physical, social and economic problems of the adolescent girls of secondary schools. *Ph.D. thesis, University of Gauhati*.
- Verma, M. (2012). *Youth Problem Inventory Agra* : National psychological corporation.
- Verma, S. & Ojha, S. (2005). Behavioural Problems in Adolescent: Some preventive Measures. *Praachi Journal of Psycho- Cultural Dimensions*. 21 (2), 152-154.